

The Government's Capital Expenditure: A View from Central Government and Local Government in Indonesia

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Abstract

The Government's main role is to serve the public and ensure the fulfilment of social needs. Public facilities are essential to support the national prosperity and development. Capital expenditure becomes one of the financial instruments that can be allocated to build infrastructures as the part of public service. The research aim to figure out the performance of central and local government in spending the income to public investment. The study conducts ten years analysis to financial report of local government in West Java Province-Indonesia. There are 30 data sample from Bogor, Depok and Bekasi City, that proceeded into statistical analysis using multiple regressions. The result shows that both central and local government have optimize their income capacity especially in dedicated funds and budget surplus toward capital expenditure. The regression remains a significant influence from independent variable to dependent variable. The research contributes to the completion of previous study in the government investment especially the relation of central and local government.

Keywords: *Government Investment Feasibility, Public Infrastructure, Regional Development*

1. Introduction

Economic, social and cultural aspects are instrumental in determining the feasibility of government capital expenditure (GCE) for local governments. Social and cultural aspects characterize capital expenditure decisions that are not made by the private sector. The target of these two aspects is the fulfilment of local government obligations in serving the needs of public facilities for the community. On the other hand, the economic aspect, which focuses on the rate of return on investment, cannot be ignored. The regional autonomy policy in effect in Indonesia requires local governments to be more independent in managing revenues and expenditures. However, the central government is still obliged to assist local governments with limited revenue sources to realize development priorities in the region.

Central government assistance mainly used for certain capital expenditures is known as a dedicated fund (DF). The use of the DF mostly at the construction, procurement of goods, improvement and improvement of public facilities oriented to public services with a long economic life (1). Thus, local governments can provide public services more optimally.

Apart from assistance from the central government, regional governments that have autonomy can take advantage of the budget surplus (BS) for regional development needs. A budget surplus can occur when revenue exceeds realized regional government spending (2,3). The surplus in local government budgets will return in term of regional development. In the end, public service must be the top priority of a government.

Research on the contribution of the central government to regional development proves that infrastructure development in the regions is accelerating (4–6). Besides, regions that are not yet financially independent rely heavily on central government assistance in fulfilling the regional budgets. In contrast to developed regions, the contribution of the central government is not significant, because local governments have adequate sources of income. Capital expenditures are proven to accelerate the economic rate of a region and encourage national economic growth (7,8). Previous research has discussed the contribution of the regional and central government in the amount of capital expenditure but did not reveal the size of the contribution of each party (9,10). This research has significant aims to do so that the government has a clear sight of financial strength in meeting public needs. Also, it is necessary to study the impact of the central government's contribution to regional government capital expenditures to provide a new perspective among this research area. Through dedicated

funds and budget surplus, this research will reveal the variable that has a more significant effect on local government capital expenditures.

2. Literature Overview

2.1 Government Capital Expenditures

In most developing countries, there is a separation between routine and development budgets. The budget that uses to carry out development or public sector investment is also known as capital expenditure. In its implementation, capital expenditure budgeting is facing the following constraints: (1) ensuring that capital expenditures are carried out, solving various public social problems, through one investment activity; (2) estimating expenses that will arise in the future as a result of the investment program; (3) evaluating the programs that have been carried out and finding their relevance to the program's implementation; (4) perform investment feasibility analysis (11). General evaluation of the feasibility of government investment consist of 4 aspects: (1) technical aspects; (2) social and cultural aspects; economic and financial aspects; distribution aspect (12).

2.2 Dedicated Funds (The Specific Allocation)

Funds intent to assist regions in funding regional capital expenditures in the form of facilities and infrastructure for the community such as education, health and public facilities in order to accelerate regional development and achieve national development priorities. The special allocation funds help reduce the burden on the costs of particular activities that are borne by local governments (13). Partially the dedicated fund variable has a significant effect on capital expenditure. Other studies have shown that the dedicated funds for road infrastructure, which are allocated by the central government to maintain and improve the performance of road infrastructure services in the regions, are proven to support regional economic development (14).

2.3 Local Government's Budget Surplus

A budget surplus is an indicator that describes the efficiency of government spending. A budget surplus can be used as an indicator of the efficiency of government spending because this will only occur if there is a surplus in the regional government budget and there is favourable net financing from the budget deficit (15). An idle budget surplus for capital expenditure can lead to the formation of *idle money* and lead to the poor performance of public services in a local government. Efforts must be made to optimize the budget surplus that can build regional progress (16).

3. Methodology

This study looked at a 10-year series of data (2008-2018) obtained from local government financial reports in the province of West Java (Depok City, Bekasi City, and Bogor City). We observe financial reports that have been audited by the Supreme Audit Agency of the Republic of Indonesia to ensure data quality. After reducing various data available in a financial report, we obtained three primary data, namely budget surplus, special allocation funds and government capital expenditure. This data was then statistically tested using the normality test, autocorrelation, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity (17). In conducting data analysis, the strength of the relationship between special allocation funds and budget surpluses with capital expenditures is seen from the coefficient of determination (r^2). The resulting model is multiple linear regression.

4. Results and Discussion

The results of data testing in this study are as follow:

Table 1 Research Hypothesis Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	R	R Square
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	17,144	6,501		2,930	0,00	0,677	0,458
	DF	3,364	0,377	1,010	2,118	0,00		
	BS	4,488	0,240	2,549	3,841	0,00		

Source: Data Analysis SPSS Ver. 22, 2020

With an increase in the special allocation funds provided by the central government to regional governments, there will be an increase in regional government capital spending. This indicates that there is a positive correlation between special allocation funds and local government capital expenditures. Funds that have been specifically designated for use by the central government require local governments to spend these funds following directions from the central government (18). This is why the special allocation funds can be useful in building public facilities owned by local governments. Thus, public services felt by the community will have a direct impact through the particular allocation fund program from the central government.

With the assistance of special allocation funds from the central government, local governments make allocations of their revenue sources to other priorities or even economize so that a budget surplus is formed. This study shows that the budget surplus that occurs in local governments in the province of West Java is optimized for regional development (19). This statistical results, which show that an increase in the budget surplus will increase the amount of capital expenditures issued by the government. Thus, the positive correlation between budget surpluses and capital expenditures shows that the efforts of the central government in supporting regional development are welcomed through budget efficiency by local governments, and the results of this efficiency are returned to the community, through the provision of public facilities for the community (20,21).

This research shows that there is always a budget surplus for 10 consecutive years in local governments in the West Java region. Although the amount is relatively fluctuating, Figure 1 shows that there is a budget surplus showing that local governments can make regional government spending efficient and optimize local revenue. In Figure 2, the special allocation funds are focused on 2017, 2018 and 2019. It can be seen that there is a sharp increase in special allocation funds, not directly proportional to changes in the budget surplus graph. It can be inferred that local governments do not depend on special allocation funds in realizing local government budgets (22).

Figure 1 Budget Surplus

Figure 2 Dedicated Funds

Movement of regional government capital expenditures reached its highest level in 2016. This could happen due to the budget surplus in 2015, reaching its highest point, so that in the 2016 fiscal year, the budget surplus was optimized for the government capital expenditures area. Statistically, this research is successful in proving this, that the budget surplus affects local government capital expenditures.

Figure 3 Capital Expenditure

Figure 3 shows that local governments in the province of West Java, are increasingly improving services to the public, through increased capital spending.

5. Conclusion

This research has succeeded in revealing the influence of special allocation funds and budget surpluses in regional governments in the province of West Java on capital expenditures. Thus, this can become a concern for the central government to make comparisons against similar variables in other regions in Indonesia. This needs to be done considering that equitable distribution of national development is the obligation of the central government, and this research can be used as a reference to measure the seriousness of local governments in managing budgets, especially budget surpluses and special allocation funds (2,5,17). This study also shows that the budget surplus has a more dominant effect on capital expenditure compared to special allocation funds.

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